

INFLATION AND ECONOMIC MISERY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Nigeria is presently bedeviled by severe economic hardship, which threatens the survival of many Nigerians especially the poor. This study aims to establish the causal link between inflation and economic misery in Nigerian in order to understand and address the complex interplay between inflation and wellbeing. The study adopted the Tado-Yamamoto Dynamic Granger Causality Test approach in estimating the results of the study. The results of the study indicate that, on the one hand, inflation rate and bank lending rate granger-cause economic hardship, while unemployment rate and per capita GDP growth rate have bi-directional causal relationship with economic hardship, on the other. The findings emphasized the dire need for structural reforms targeted at urgently improving agricultural productivity, reducing dependence on imports, and the fostering of a stable political and economic environment to improve/build investors' confidence with a view to attracting the necessary investments for sustainable growth and curbing inflation.

Key words: Economic misery, inflation, unemployment, sustainable growth

1. INTRODUCTION

Misery is an economic concept created by Arthur Okun in the 1970's to explain the economic discomfort of a country contributed by the simultaneous existence of rising unemployment and inflation in an economy at a particular period of time. The United States was used as a snapshot to this effect (Halton, 2023). Hanke (2014) computed the misery index as the sum of unemployment and inflation rates, explaining that the index helps determine how the average citizen is doing economically and is calculated by adding the seasonally adjusted unemployment rate to the annual inflation rate. Halton (2023) stressed that since unemployment and inflation are both considered detrimental to any economy, their combined value is useful as an indicator of overall economic health and well-being of the people and this is known as the misery index.

The recent misery index worked on by Hanke (2014), added bank lending rate and GDP per capita growth rate; thus, given the index as the addition of unemployment, inflation and bank lending rates minus the growth rate of per capita GDP. The performances of these variables have

substantial influence on the misery index. The high rates of the first three variables and low rate of the fourth will inadvertently raise the index and worsen misery level among the population (Dauda, 2023). A high or worsening misery index has the capacity to degenerate the level of poverty and hurt the poor because the poor suffer most from the adverse performance of either or all of the various components of the index (Dauda, 2023).

According to Dauda, (2023), the misery index in Nigeria rose from about 61.2 in the fourth quarter of 2022 to around 73.1 in the second quarter of 2023. The recent report of Steve Hanke’s Annual Misery Index (HAMI) on 156 countries shows Nigeria moving from the 15th position in 2020 to 11th in 2021 worldwide and the fourth Africa. The implication is that the country is the 11th most miserable nation globally and the fourth in the continent of Africa, respectively. The present annual misery index using the Hanks index valuation stands at 53% on average with each quarter having values between 50-70% on average in 2023.

Among the Hanken annual misery index indicators, inflation is the most volatile. The Central Bank of Nigeria, (2020), defines inflation as the rate of increase in prices over a given period of time. Inflation is typically a broad measure, such as the overall increase in prices or the increase in the cost of living in a country. More specifically, it is the persistent rise in the general price level of goods and services in an economy over a period of time (Oner, 2020). According to the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (2022), inflation rate in Nigeria averaged 13.0% in the ten years to 2022. More recently, inflation rate stands at about 33.6% (NBS, 2024). The most well-known indicator of inflation is the Consumer Price Index (CPI), which measures the percentage change in the price of a basket of goods and services consumed by households. This upward swing in inflation in Nigeria in this current and last administration is expected to impact heavily on the misery index.

According to NBS, (2023), month-on-month inflation has increased since the present administration while also having a higher variance. In **Figure 1**, food inflation was the highest in August, 2023 and February, 2024 followed by headline inflation.

Figure 1: Inflation month – on – month % of past administration and present administration
Source: NBS, 2024

In **Figure 2**, the year-on-year change in inflation has also increased since the present administration. According to NBS (2023) on the latest consumer price index and inflation, headline inflation climbed to 33.95% by May 2024. Food inflation rose to 37.95% in March and 40.66% in May 2024. The rising inflation is untamed by the present government regime in Nigeria.

Figure 2: Inflation year – on – year % of past administration and present administration
 Source: NBS, 2024

The other factor very important in the estimation of the misery index is unemployment. The unemployment rate in Nigeria which is not as volatile as inflation rate still remains problematic, even though it has not risen as fiercely as the inflation rate. Nigeria’s unemployment rate according to the World Bank (2023) stands at 5%.

Indicators	Q4 2022	Q1 2023	Q2 2023	Q3 2023
Labour Force Participation Rate	77.8	74.9	80.4	74.5
Employment-to-population Ratio	73.6	76.6	77.1	75.6
Share of employed people in self-employment	84.0	86.0	88.0	87.8
Own-use Producer of foodstuff	5.6	3.9	4.8	4.1
Youth Unemployment Rate	8.3	6.9	7.2	8.6
Urban Unemployment Rate	6.3	5.4	5.9	6.0
Rural Unemployment	4.0	3.9	2.5	4.0
Wage Employment Rate	13.4	11.8	12.0	12.7
Informal Employment	93.5	92.6	92.7	92.3

Table 1: Employment and unemployment rates for past and present administration
 Source, NBS, 2024

However, in **Table 1**, NBS put youth unemployment, urban unemployment and rural unemployment in 3rd quarter of 2023 at 8.6%, 6.0% and 4.0% respectively. The size of the labour force decreased in 3rd quarter of 2023, evidenced by the participation rate and employment-to-population ratio. Youth unemployment increased in 3rd quarter of 2023. Urban unemployment increased marginally, while rural unemployment grew significantly. This is due to the rise in population that has outpaced economic growth in the country. Ubah (2021), asserts that another probable cause unemployment is that foreign and domestic investment are not sufficient and with the current economic situation, there is not much incentive to invest in Nigeria.

Furthermore, stability of the economy is not guaranteed in the face of high inflation as many economic activities are halted down. Economic growth is hindered as risk of uncertainties in price fluctuation discourage investment and business expansion. NBS, (2024) postulates that persistent inflation largely contributed to exchange rate volatility.

Figure 3: Monthly exchange rate from 1999 - 2024
 Source: NBS, 2024

Money loses its value during inflation. Its purchasing power keeps depreciating. Consumers cannot afford to buy much with the same amount of money as prices of commodities are persistently shooting up. The situation is worsened with depreciating and high volatility of the exchange rates as seen in **Figure 3**.

Although there are studies such as Smith, (2020), Jones, (2019) that investigated the effect of inflation on economic hardship, however, the investigation of the causal relationship between inflation and economic misery in Nigeria has been largely neglected and this study seeks to fill this gap and so provide a more nuanced insight into menace of inflation in the economy.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Review

World Bank, (2021) theorized that high level of poverty and unemployment prevalent in an inflationary economy cause economic hardship as prices of goods and services keep hitting the roof. Consequently, the Poor masses face untold hardship as they are exposed to hunger and starvation. Low-income earners hardly meet up their basic needs for food let alone healthcare services as income is eaten up by inflation. According to the World Bank (2022), about 95.1 million Nigerians were living below the national poverty line due to the compounding effects of inflation and economic stagnation. The minimum wage set at #30,000.00, though has now been reviewed upwards to #70,000.00 per month, has not kept pace with the rising inflation leading to a decline in real wages, making it increasingly difficult for individuals to afford basic necessities. Housing costs in major cities have surged by over 30%, further straining the household budget. The cumulative effect of these factors is reflected in the misery index, which highlights the severe impact of high inflation and unemployment.

Okun’s Law

The theoretical framework relevant to explaining economic discomfort is the Okun’s law of misery index. Arthur Okun was the first economist who developed a misery index in 1966, used to measure the level of misery or economic discomfort among the citizens in an economy. According to this index, the loss in general welfare and level of objective economic malaise was specified as the unweighted sum of the annual inflation and unemployment rates.

That is, $MI = \pi + U$ (1)

Where: MI = Misery Index; π =Annual Inflation rate; U =Total unemployment rate.

In recent times, however, the Okun’s misery index has been subjected to series of criticisms on the basis of oversimplification. To this end, the original Okun’s misery index was slightly modified by Steve Hanke in 2019. Hanke (2019), modified the Okun’s misery index by taking the sum of the inflation, unemployment and bank lending rates, minus the percentage change in real GDP per capita. This is expressed symbolically as:

$MI = \pi + U + R - \Delta Y$ (2)

Where: MI, π and U, are as defined in equation (1); R = Bank lending rate; ΔY = Percentage change in real GDP per capita.

Higher readings on the first three variables in equation (2) in his words, are “bad” and make people miserable. On the other hand, higher readings on the fourth variable (GDP per capita growth) are “good” and are thus subtracted from the sum of the “bads”, to offset the misery index.

2.2. Empirical Review

While the present study only seeks to understand the causal links between inflation and economic misery in Nigeria, several studies have articulated empirically various outcomes of inflation on macroeconomic variables and on economic growth. For instance, Akinlo, (2024) investigated corruption and misery index in Nigeria, looking for a link over the period 1980–2018 using the autoregressive distributed lag model. The results show that the level of corruption is closely related to the country’s dire economic conditions. These findings suggest that inflation and unemployment rates need to be reduced in the country using the appropriate monetary and fiscal policies. Moreover, government efforts at increasing economic activity in the country will reduce the level of corruption, especially in the long run.

George-Anokwuru, (2023) investigated monetary policy and misery index in Nigeria spanning 1985 to 2019. The misery index was measured by the sum of unemployment, inflation, and lending rates minus the percentage change in Real Gross Domestic Product per capita. The results revealed that monetary policy rate and exchange rate have a significant relationship with the misery index in Nigeria during the period of study. However, there is no significant relationship between the broad money supply and the misery index in Nigeria during the period of study. The study concluded that though monetary policy has the potential of reducing the misery index in Nigeria but it has not been well managed to reduce the misery index in Nigeria during the period of study. That is, monetary policy has not been effective in reducing the misery index in Nigeria during the period of study.

Audi and Ali, (2023) investigated public policy and economic misery nexus among developed and developing countries from 1987 to 2019. The empirical findings of the article show level of domestic investment, foreign debt, and government revenue are discouraging economic misery among developing countries. Whereas economic development and the level of the population are encouraging economic misery among developing countries. The level of domestic investment is promoting economic misery in developed countries, but government revenue and economic development are reducing economic misery among developed countries. In the case of the whole sample analysis, the level of domestic investment and government revenues decreases the level of economic misery, but the level of population, foreign debt, and economic development depresses the economic misery.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Model for the Study

This model is concerned with exploring the effects of inflation on economic misery in Nigeria and we adopt the model of Hanke (2019). From the foregoing, the model for the study is specified in the functional form as:

$$MI = F (I + U + R - \Delta Y) \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where: MI = Misery Index; I = Inflation and, U = Unemployment; R = Bank lending rate; ΔY = Percentage change in real GDP per capita.

3.2. Estimation Technique

The author study used Tado-Yamamoto dynamic Granger Causality test approach to estimate the causal relationship between inflation and economic misery proxied by the misery index. The Tado-Yamamoto dynamic Granger Causality is adopted in order to overcome the problem of non-stationary or uncorrelated error terms. Testing for Granger-causality using F-statistic when one or more time series are non-stationary could lead to spurious causality.

The Toda and Yamamoto multivariate framework of our case study can be stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 MI_t = & \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=1}^{k+dmax} \beta_{1i} MI_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+dmax} \beta_{1i} Infr_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+dmax} \beta_{1i} Unmpr_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \\
 & + \sum_{i=1}^{k+dmax} \beta_{1i} BLr_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+dmax} \beta_{1i} PGr_{t-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 1
 \end{aligned}$$

Where: MI is the misery index; Infr is the inflation rate; Unmpr is the unemployment rate; BLr is the bank lending rate; and PGr is the per capita growth rate.

4. RESULTS ANALYSIS

4.1. Tado-Yamamoto dynamic Granger Causality Test

This test is conducted to see whether there is a causal relationship that exists between economic misery and inflation. The hypothesis testing is thus:

H₀: There is no causal relationship between the variables

H₁: There is a causal relationship between the variables

The decision rule is to accept the alternative hypothesis that there is a causal relationship between the variables if the probability value (P Value) is less than the 0.05 level of significance chosen in the study. However, we will accept the null hypothesis if otherwise.

Table 1: Results of the Tado-Yamamoto dynamic Granger Causality Test

Dependent/ Variable	Sources of Causation				
	MI χ^2	Infr χ^2	unempr	Blr	PGr
MI	26.4521*	-	14.9567**	-	10.4632**
Infr	29.8034*				
unempr	16.7864**				
Blr	12.7894**				
PGr	17.9243*				

Note: ***, ** and * indicate significance at the 1 %, 5 % and 10 % respectively.

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024, using E-view 10.0

The results of the Tado-Yamamoto dynamic granger causality test reveal that there is a bi-directional causality between current misery index and past misery index at 1% level of significance. For inflation rate and misery index, causality flows from inflation rate to economic misery at 1% level of significance. However, there is a bi-directional causal relationship exists between economic misery and unemployment rate at 5% level of significance on the one hand and economic misery and per capita GDP growth rate at 1% and 5% level of significance respectively. Bank lending rate is found to granger-cause economic misery with no reverse causation.

5. DISCUSSIONS

Inflation has been found to cause economic misery in Nigeria. There is no doubt that economic misery has worsened from the beginning of the present administration. As observed by World Bank (2022), about 95.1 million Nigerians were living below the national poverty line due to the compounding effects of inflation. Now that inflation rate has hit the roof with no solution in sight, poverty rate is expected to increase as more people slide into abject poverty. This drastic increase indicates that more citizens are finding it difficult to afford food, clothing, shelter, healthcare, energy, transport, and other basic needs. Prices of household commodities have doubled and, in some cases, tripled, and the income/salary of the majority still remains the same despite the rapid surge in inflation, and the resultant effect of this is economic misery and untold hardship. Staples such as rice, bread, and maize have seen unprecedented price hikes, which directly impact the poor and vulnerable populations who spend a large proportion of their income on food.

Figure 5: Pictorial evidence of protesting masses over economic hardship
Source: Daily Sun Newspaper, April, 2024

Figure 5 shows pictorial evidence of the frustration and economic hardship faced by the people during the present administration in 2024 exemplified by the protesting masses. The Nigerian government and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) have attempted various measures to combat inflation, including tightening monetary policy and implementing fiscal reforms. CBN has also raised interest rates to curb excessive spending and reduce money supply, aiming to stabilise prices. However, these measures have had limited success, as structural issues such as inadequate infrastructure, insecurity, and dependence on imports continue to drive inflationary pressures upwards.

Furthermore, unemployment and economic hardship were found to have bi-directional causal relationship. This implies that economic hardship cause unemployment and unemployment causes economic hardship. This is in tandem with the study by World Bank, (2021) who found that high level of poverty and unemployment prevalent in an inflationary economy cause economic hardship as prices of goods and services keep hitting the roof.

6. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

6.1. Conclusion

In conclusion, we can see that using the trend analysis and empirical methodology, inflation rate is a big factor that causes increasing misery in Nigeria and contributing a large portion to economic hardship, which drives many persons in the country to the existential precipice. Even those who are actively employed are affected by the increasing rate of inflation because the real per capita income has significantly diminished. Investments are not even encouraged to boost productivity as a result of the high lending rate. Thus, all these phenomena occurring simultaneously continue to cause increasing misery. This has negative impact on Nigeria's economy as money would lose its purchasing power, real household income impaired, standard of living drastically jeopardized, social vices such as kidnapping, human trafficking and banditry increased, rise in unemployment and hunger become the order of the day as is presently experienced in Nigeria. In conclusion, inflation is a significant driver of economic misery in Nigeria. It erodes purchasing power, exacerbates poverty, and hampers economic stability. Without addressing this underlying issue, Nigerians are likely to remain trapped in a vicious cycle of poverty so much so that living becomes extremely difficult for majority of Nigerians leading to the existential question.

6.2. Policy Implication

The findings of the study observed trends in inflation and unemployment on economic misery in Nigeria, thus policymakers should consider adjusting minimum wage policies to account for inflation and implementing job creation strategies focused on high-employment sectors. This may involve revisiting the minimum wage framework to introduce periodic adjustments based on inflation levels, as well as expanding programs that support job growth in sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and services.

This becomes relevant as the findings suggests that the current minimum wage does not keep up with inflation, reducing its effectiveness in maintaining workers' purchasing power and addressing poverty and economic misery. Additionally, high unemployment indicates that there are not enough job opportunities, especially for the youth. If unaddressed, these issues could lead to increased poverty and increasing economic misery. This implication is particularly relevant for low-income workers, who are most affected by the declining real value of wages. It also impacts unemployed individuals, especially youth, who face limited job prospects. Additionally, policymakers and economic development agencies are crucial stakeholders, as they will be responsible for implementing these adjustments and job-creating initiatives.

Looking forward, addressing Nigeria's inflation crisis requires a comprehensive approach that goes beyond monetary tightening. Structural reforms are necessary to improve agricultural productivity, reduce dependence on imports, and enhance the supply chain infrastructure. Also, fostering a stable political and economic environment can help build investor confidence and attract the necessary investments for sustainable growth. Issues bothering on power and energy sectors, logistics and forex should also be prioritized in other to tame inflation. Epileptic power supply is detrimental to business growth in Nigeria. Owing to increased energy cost, production cost has increased. Rise in exchange rate raised prices of imported raw materials and other consumables. Again, it is high time Nigeria look inwards to tackle her problems using her resources. Reducing cost of governance will go a long way to tackle inflation in Nigeria. It is senseless buying SUV for members of the National Assembly after borrowing whooping

\$1.5billion for budget support. It is obvious that inflation could not be tackled in the midst of this flamboyant spending.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

This work empirically investigated Inflation and Economic Misery in the last decade (2014-2024). However, future research could examine inflation and economic misery trends on a regional basis to capture geographical disparities. This would provide insights into how these economic factors vary across regions and suggest more localized policy responses. More so, further research could conduct a longitudinal study to assess the long-term effects of specific policy interventions, such as minimum wage adjustments and job creation programs, on inflation and unemployment over time. This would help evaluate the effectiveness of these policies and inform future economic planning.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization: B.I.U, and J.O.O.; Methodology: J.O.O. and B.I. U.; Software: G.A.E., and M.U.A.; Validation: M. U. A. and G. A. E.; Formal analysis: B.I.U, J.O.O. and G.A.E.; Investigation: M.U.A. and G.A.E.; Resources: B.I.U and G.A.E.; Data curation: M.U.A. and J.O.O.; Writing—original draft preparation: B.I.U. and J.O.O; Writing—review and editing: G.A.E, B.I.U. and J.O.O.; All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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